

Cultural Variation in Aggressive Behavior: A Cross-Cultural Comparison of Students' Exposure to Bullying Across 32 Countries

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Abstract

Introduction. The prevalence rates of bullying vary significantly across countries and continents. Specifically, UNESCO estimates that the prevalence rates vary from 22.8% (Central America) to 48.2% (Sub-Saharan Africa). Recently these differences among countries and regions have been attributed to culture- and country-level variables. Thus, the first purpose of this study is to examine the comparability of bullying in schools across countries. Secondly, a cross-cultural comparison of the latent mean scores of bullying is implemented.

Method. The data of 286,481 adolescent students ($M=15.78$, $SD=0.29$) from 32 countries were analyzed using multilevel confirmatory factor analyses (MLCFA) and multigroup factor alignment.

Results. Results indicated that the meaning of bullying is equivalent within and between cultures. However, cross-cultural differences in bullying are apparent. East Asian countries have the lowest latent means of bullying, while Southeast Asian countries have the highest means. Anglo-Saxon, Eastern European, Mediterranean, South American, and Middle East countries displayed rather higher scores.

Discussion and Conclusion. These findings underscore the existence of cross-cultural differential responding in bullying measures. Further, the implicit role of culture as an important variable that determines the rates of bullying is underscored.

Keywords: school bullying; PISA 2018; cross-cultural research; individualism

Resumen

Introducción. Las tasas de prevalencia del acoso escolar varían significativamente entre países y continentes. En concreto, la UNESCO estima que las tasas de prevalencia varían entre el 22,8% (América Central) y el 48,2% (África subsahariana). Recientemente, estas diferencias entre países y regiones se han atribuido a variables culturales y nacionales. Por lo tanto, el primer propósito de este estudio es examinar la comparabilidad del acoso escolar de todos entre países. En segundo lugar, se realiza una comparación transcultural de las puntuaciones medias latentes del acoso escolar.

Método. Los datos de 286.481 estudiantes adolescentes ($M=15.78$, $SD=0.29$) de 32 países se analizaron mediante análisis factorial confirmatorio multinivel (MLCFA) y alineación factorial multigrupo.

Resultados. Los resultados indicaron que el significado del acoso es equivalente dentro y entre culturas. Sin embargo, las diferencias transculturales en el acoso son evidentes. Los países de Asia oriental tienen las medias latentes más bajas de acoso escolar, mientras que los países del sudeste asiático tienen las medias más altas. Los países anglosajones, de Europa del Este, mediterráneo, sudamericano y Oriente Medio mostraron puntuaciones bastante más altas.

Discusión y Conclusion: Estos resultados subrayan la existencia de una respuesta diferencial transcultural en las medidas de acoso escolar. Además, se subraya el papel implícito de la cultura como una variable importante que determina los índices de acoso escolar.

Palabras clave: acoso escolar; PISA 2018; investigación transcultural; individualismo

Introduction

Nowadays, among the most pressing issues in school psychology is the scientific inquiry into the antecedents and prevalence rates of bullying in schools. Bullying has become a problem given the increased cross-national prevalence of bullying (OECD, 2019b; Smith & Morita, 2011). Significant progress has been made in the investigation of the protective factors that reduce the manifestation of aggressive behaviours in schools. The term “bullying” refers to aggressive behaviour (Smith & Morita, 2011; UNESCO, 2019) that is repetitive, intentional, aiming to harm and is a product of an imbalance of power (Migliaccio & Raskauskas, 2015; Olweus & Limber, 2010; Smith, 2016). Despite the significant progress that has been made in terms of understanding the school-, family-, and individual-level determinants of bullying, the research into the country- and culture-specific factors that influence bullying is sparse and has produced mixed findings. Therefore, in the present study, an explanatory approach was adopted seeking to (a) confirm that the bullying construct is comparable across cultures; (b) examine whether cross-cultural differences in bullying are apparent, and, if so, how national culture may differentiate the school bullying rates.

Cross-Cultural Differences in Bullying

Research has examined differences in bullying rates across culturally diverse regions and countries. For instance, Pörhölä et al. (2016) have studied the differences in bullying prevalence rates with higher education students in four countries with different national cultures, namely Argentina, USA, Finland, and Estonia. These researchers ranked the countries as follows: Argentina (25%), USA (11%), Finland (5%), and Estonia (2%). Finally, they concluded that these discrepancies reflect national differences in cultural, socioeconomic, and education-related factors. In another study by Hilton et al. (2010), a cross-cultural comparison of factors that are associated with school bullying has been extensively presented. These authors have examined cultural differences between a highly individualistic Western nation, namely USA, and a highly collectivist Eastern nation, namely Japan. They found that bullying in both nations is a common issue; however, there are distinctions between the two nations in terms of personal, family- and school-related predictors of bullying. Another cross-cultural study by Samara and colleagues (2019) drew a total sample of 3,186 school children from Israel (Jewish Israelis and Arab Palestinian Israelis), Palestine (the Gaza Strip), Germany, and Greece. This study found statistically significant differences (via chi-square tests) in bullying between all cultural groups. Specifically, it was shown that Greece had the highest rates, fol-

lowed by Germany, Israel (Jewish), the Gaza Strip, and Israel (Palestinians) (Samara et al., 2019).

More recently, the *Health Behaviour in School-aged Children* (Inchley et al., 2020) international survey has administered a single item asking European and Canadian students whether they have been bullied in the past couple of months. The results of comparative analyses were presented as proportions of students who had reported being bullied at least two or three times in the past couple of months. In general, the rankings of the countries showed that Eastern European countries had higher rates of bullying compared to the Mediterranean and North European countries (see Inchley et al., 2020). The *Programme for International Student Assessment* (PISA- OECD, 2019b) has also presented cross-cultural comparative results. As shown in OECD (2019b), PISA 2018 examined the proportion and prevalence of bullying across nations. Brunei Darussalam, the Dominican Republic, Indonesia, Morocco, and the Philippines had the highest rates of school bullying, whereas China, Iceland, Japan, the Netherlands, and Chinese Taipei had the lowest rates (OECD, 2019b). Despite this, the Item Response Theory scaling that PISA 2018 utilized standardised bullying with respect to the OECD countries' average bullying score, which does not reflect individual students' scores on bullying (OECD, 2019a). Furthermore, as presented in UNESCO (2019), Central America had the lowest percentage of bullying (22.8%). Europe and the Caribbean regions had similar prevalence rates (25%), whereas North American and South American regions were characterized by slightly higher rates (31.7% and 30.2%, respectively). The Middle East and North African areas had also similar percentages of bullying (i.e., 41.1% and 42.7%, respectively). Finally, the highest rates were found in Sub-Saharan Africa (48.2%).

Overall, it can be argued that prior cross-cultural comparisons were based on observed measures that cannot accurately reflect the multidimensional nature of bullying using a latent variable approach. Additionally, comparisons of observed scores do not account for measurement error inherent in all measures. Therefore, more accurate and nuanced methodologies are needed to clarify when and how cross-cultural variation in bullying occurs.

The Issue of Measurement Equivalence in Cross-Cultural Educational Research

Cross-cultural comparisons in educational research presuppose that the same construct is similarly construed (i.e., has the same psychological meaning) and measured across different cultural groups (Davidov et al., 2014). This property of a comparable measure is known as

measurement invariance/ equivalence (Kline, 2016). In principle, this means that any comparison between culturally diverse groups without prior examination of measurement equivalence can result in biased conclusions. Measurement equivalence is typically examined via multiple-group confirmatory factor analysis (MGCFA- Davidov et al., 2014). Generally, there are three tiers of measurement equivalence that are of interest in cross-cultural comparisons. The first tier is referred to as configural invariance/ equivalence and concerns the extent to which a factor/measurement model is configured similarly in all groups (Brown, 2015; Kline, 2016). The second tier of equivalence is called ‘weak’ or ‘metric’. If this level of equivalence is achieved, then we can assume that the construct (in this case, bullying) has the same metric; that is, the participants show a similar comprehension of the meaning of the items (i.e., psychological meaning) (Kline, 2016). Finally, the highest tier of equivalence is called ‘scalar’ or ‘strong’. This level of equivalence is required to meaningfully compare the variable’s means across groups (Putnick & Bornstein, 2016). Strong equivalence indicates that, if participants from different (cultural) groups have the same latent trait level, then they will obtain the same score on the scale (Kline, 2016).

As the psychometric literature indicates (e.g., Byrne & Van de Vijver, 2014; Kim et al., 2017), when the number of cultural groups is large (>10), a cross-group examination of measurement equivalence employing multigroup confirmatory factor analysis (MGCFA) becomes cumbersome. As an alternative, a multilevel confirmatory factor analysis (MLCFA) can be utilized to assess the measurement equivalence of bullying within and between cultures. In line with the cross-level measurement equivalence literature (e.g., Byrne & Van de Vijver, 2014; Cheung et al., 2006; Stapleton et al., 2016), the first test of multilevel equivalence concerns whether the factor structure is configured similarly at both levels (multilevel configural model). In other words, the first step is to see whether the pattern of latent variables, observed indicators, and possible residual correlations is equivalent across levels. The second stage of multilevel measurement equivalence is to test whether the factor loadings are equal across levels (metric equivalence - Stapleton, 2016). To test the hypothesis of strong measurement equivalence in the context of MLCFA, the residual variance (θ) at the culture level must be constrained to zero (Jak, 2016; Muthen & Asparouhov, 2018).

Equivalence analyses with a large number of groups are often impractical because of a substantial degree of non-equivalence (Byrne & Van de Vijver, 2017; Muthen & Asparouhov, 2018) that is typically attributable to differences in participants’ and nations’ characteristics

(Muthen & Asparouhov, 2018). Given that strong measurement equivalence is hard to establish in the context of large-scale cross-cultural surveys (Byrne & Van de Vijver, 2017), a new technique has been recently developed which is called the 'multigroup factor analysis alignment' (Asparouhov & Muthen, 2014). The alignment method can help with bypassing the issue of strong measurement non-equivalence (Kline, 2016). This method begins with the estimation of the typical MGCFA configural model. It is underscored that the alignment optimization does not degrade the fit of the configural model (Asparouhov & Muthen, 2014). Next, the method utilizes techniques similar to factor rotation in exploratory factor analysis to minimize the degree of non-equivalence in loadings and intercepts/ thresholds and, ultimately, to estimate latent factor means (μ_i) and standard deviations (ψ_i). It is noted that the alignment optimization is a non-parametric method and, thus, it does not require multivariate normality (Byrne & Van de Vijver, 2017). The only assumptions for this method are a good-fitting configurally equivalent model and a low degree of non-equivalence. Specifically, the alignment procedure can produce meaningful and trustworthy estimates of the latent factor means when there is less than 25% of non-equivalence (Asparouhov & Muthen, 2014; Byrne & Van de Vijver, 2017; Fisher & Karl, 2019; Pokropek et al., 2019).

Despite the possibility to apply the alignment method, when the assumption of strong measurement equivalence is *not* tenable, this means that cross-cultural differences exist. Additionally, this indicates a differential additive response style and that other factors beyond the latent variable of interest (i.e., bullying) exert an effect on what options of this scale the respondents endorse (Katsantonis, 2020; Kline, 2016). The next step after strong measurement non-equivalence would be to identify some culture-related variables that may influence the scores on the non-equivalent measure to explain cross-cultural differences (Poortinga et al., 2002). Therefore, the effect of national culture on bullying should be discussed next.

Can National Culture Explain Bullying in Schools?

Culture is too complex to concisely define and many researchers do not concede on an operationalization of the construct. Hofstede's (2001) definition of culture is adopted, which states that culture is "the collective programming of the mind that distinguishes one group or category of people from another" (p. 9). When the word "culture" is used, it usually refers to national culture. Although some criticize the model of national cultures (see Williamson, 2002), an analysis of the *World Values Study* database (Minkov & Hofstede, 2012) has shown

that, despite the existence of some within-culture variation, the nations do not overlap and people from the same nation score consistently on cultural values indices.

To understand, though, the cultural determinants of bullying, I turn to the major cross-cultural study by Hofstede (2001). In the late 60s to early 70s, Geert Hofstede carried out a major cross-national survey of IBM employees. He observed that the responses were similar within countries and reflected predictable patterns of dissimilarities across countries, which indicated differential scoring on the most fundamental value orientations (Minkov, 2013). In short, based on ecological correlations and factor analyses (Hofstede & Milosevik, 2011), it was concluded that four initial dimensions were “pancultural” psychological variables. The initial four dimensions of national cultures are (a) individualism versus collectivism; (b) power distance; (c) uncertainty avoidance; (d) masculinity versus femininity (Hofstede et al., 2010). In the present study, though, only individualism will be considered because this value has garnered the attention of many researchers and has become focal to the field of Cross-Cultural Psychology (House et al., 2004).

Individualism describes a society where the people are disconnected from each other; where the identity of the unit is separate from others (Hofstede & Milosevik, 2011). In highly individualistic societies (e.g., USA, UK, Australia, Austria, Denmark, Sweden), people are expected to care on average about themselves and their immediate family or relations (Hofstede et al., 2010). In these nations, violating written and unwritten social rules results in guilt (Minkov, 2013). On the other hand, the opposite pole of the continuum, namely collectivism, refers to a society where people are focused on in-group goals (Hofstede et al., 2010). In highly collectivist societies (e.g., China, South Korea, Indonesia, Japan), people are part of highly cohesive groups, to which they owe unquestionable fealty and defend them through their lifespan (Hofstede & Milosevik, 2011). Thus, it could be argued that highly collectivist nations will display lower school bullying rates than highly individualistic nations.

Moreover, following Uskul et al. (2010) and Uskul et al. (2013), two subtypes of collectivism may be further distinguished, namely Confucian-based and honour-based collectivism. Confucian-based collectivism emphasizes modesty and harmony, whereas people in countries with honour-based collectivism value the act of protecting and maintaining a good reputation and the honour of oneself and the group. According to Uskul et al. (2010), Confucian-based collectivism characterizes mainly the East Asian countries (e.g., Japan, Korea,

China, Hong Kong), whereas honour-based collectivism is found in Mediterranean, Middle East, and Latin American countries (e.g., Argentina, Brazil, Italy, Mexico, Portugal, Arab Emirates, Spain, Greece, Turkey). Further, based on Vieluf et al. (2013), another type of collectivism, that is neither Confucian- nor honour-based, is found in Eastern European countries (e.g., Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania). These subtypes of collectivism have not been previously - as far as I know- linked with nations' bullying rates. Therefore, I argue that there is a gap in the literature that merits further study.

In light of the distinction between individualistic and collectivist nations (Hofstede et al., 2010; House et al., 2004), one would have expected to find that the association between individualism and bullying to be positive. Evidence to the contrary, though, comes from two fairly recent sources. Specifically, Smith and Robinson (2019) performed cross-cultural comparative analyses of the relation of bullying prevalence and individualism using data from large-scale international surveys. In short, these authors used ecological correlations. Ecological correlations are correlations between scores that have been aggregated at the country level (Van de Vijver et al., 2010). Smith and Robinson (2019) found that the ecological correlations of bullying and individualism were mostly negative and did not reach statistical significance at the conventional level. Regarding PISA, which is of interest for the present study, they found that the correlation between individualism and “being bullied at least a few times a month” was negative (i.e., $r(46) = -0.193, p > 0.05$), and the correlation between individualism and the “index of exposure to bullying” was positive and marginally larger than zero (i.e., $r(45) = 0.005, p > 0.05$). Other researchers (Migliaccio & Raskauskas, 2015) descriptively compared collectivist and individualistic countries based on the data of the WHO. They found that school bullying in more collectivist countries (i.e., Greece, Portugal, Lithuania) was more prevalent than in highly individualistic countries (i.e., UK, USA, Denmark, Germany, Hungary). These findings are attributed to the greater regulatory framework in highly individualistic countries (Smith et al., 2018). It is underscored that these studies did not consider the various subtypes of collectivism (see Uskul et al., 2010, 2013). By incorporating the subtypes of collectivism in the discussion, a more nuanced and accurate picture of cross-cultural variation in bullying rates should emerge.

The Present Study

Although prior studies have examined the link of individualism (vs. collectivism) with students' exposure to bullying (e.g., Migliaccio & Raskauskas, 2015; Smith & Robinson,

2019), the present study explores first whether bullying can be justifiably compared across cultures. Therefore, an important first step is the testing of the measurement equivalence of bullying. Although relative comparisons of bullying prevalence rates have been presented in prior research (e.g., Inchley et al., 2020; OECD, 2019b; Pörhölä et al., 2016; UNESCO, 2019), these comparisons were based on frequencies and percentages without the prior establishment of strong factorial equivalence, which is a vital assumption for accurate and meaningful cross-cultural comparisons of psychological outcomes (Van de Vijver & Leung, 2011). Precluding this initial step may have resulted in the positive ecological correlation between bullying and individualism found with the PISA data (see Smith & Robinson, 2019) because the psychological meaning of bullying may not be equivalent in all cultures (i.e., absence of weak equivalence). Additionally, if the psychological meaning of school bullying is not equivalent between cultures and if strong equivalence is not tenable, then any attempt at cross-cultural comparisons will be moot.

Moreover, it is underscored that prior works (Migliaccio & Raskauskas, 2015; Smith & Robinson, 2019) have been situated within the framework of individualism versus collectivism without considering different subtypes of collectivism. Thus, in this study, I go beyond a bipolar approach and draw upon the distinction of further subtypes of collectivism (i.e., honour-based vs. Confucian-based vs. eastern European) to understand better the extent to which the cultural value of individualism (vs. collectivism) differentiates the nations' scores on bullying measures. However, to reach the most accurate and meaningful conclusions, in the present approach, latent factor means are utilized to facilitate cross-cultural comparisons because they reflect the countries' exact position on the latent variable's continuum. Subsequently, the following research questions and hypotheses are formulated:

RQ1: Is bullying comparable between cultures?

RQ2: Are cross-cultural differences in bullying eminent?

RQ3: Do the latent means of individualistic, honour-based, Confucian-based, and East European collectivist nations differ?

It is hypothesized that school bullying will display measurement equivalence across cultures (hypothesis 1); however, cross-cultural differences in bullying scores will be apparent (hypothesis 2). Finally, I hypothesize that there will be no differences among the subtypes of

collectivist cultures (hypothesis 3), although, it is expected that differences between collectivist and individualistic cultures will be apparent (hypothesis 4).

Method

Participants

The sample of the present study comprises 15-year-old students ($M=15.78$, $SD=0.29$) from 32 countries. These data are part of the overall database of the seventh cycle of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA 2018), which was published in December 2019. PISA utilizes two-stage cluster sampling, where a minimum of 150 schools are sampled first and students are randomly sampled from the selected schools (OECD, 2019a). The international survey assessed cognitive skills and psychosocial conditions of students from 79 countries and economies. In the present study, a subsample of $N= 286,481$ participants from 32 countries was extracted from the overall database. These countries (see supplementary materials) were selected because they comprise a comparatively representative sample with significant cultural variation with highly individualistic countries, on one hand (i.e., USA, UK), and highly collectivist countries, on the other hand (i.e., Korea, China, Japan). Further, established scores on cultural values indices are available for these countries. PISA 2018 has received ethics approval from the relevant ethics committees in the respective countries prior to data collection. The PISA 2018 data are freely available and accessible online.

Instruments

The scale that measures the exposure of students to bullying is also coded as “being bullied” in the international database. This scale was created and administered by PISA 2018 (OECD, 2019b). The students' responses to being exposed to bullying were recorded based on 6 items. The question prompt was “During the past 12 months, how often have you had the following experiences in school?”. Four response options were made available to the respondents, namely 1 “Never or almost never”; 2 “A few times a year”; 3 “A few times a month”; 4 “Once a week or more”. All items are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. *Item Wordings of the Exposure to Bullying Scale*

1. Other students left me out of things on purpose.
2. Other students made fun of me.
3. I was threatened by other students.
4. Other students took away or destroyed things that belonged to me.
5. I got hit or pushed around by other students.
6. Other students spread nasty rumors about me.

Note: Item wordings were retrieved from OECD (2019b).

It should be noted that PISA (OECD, 2019b) utilized only the first *three* items to form their index of exposure to bullying. However, in the present study, the first five items were selected because a factor model with only three items is a just-identified model and cannot be further evaluated (Kline, 2016). Item 6 was not further considered because of the extremely low intraclass correlation coefficient ($\rho < 0.05$). Reliability coefficients for the latent variable of bullying in schools were derived from a multigroup confirmatory factor model (MGCFA). Cronbach's coefficient of internal reliability ranged across countries from $\alpha = 0.689$ to $\alpha = 0.901$. McDonald's coefficient omega ranged across countries from $\omega_H = 0.658$ to $\omega_H = 0.877$. Generally, the scale was cross-culturally a reliable measure.

Statistical Procedures

All the main analyses were conducted in the framework of the statistical language and environment *R* (R Core Team, 2018). Multilevel confirmatory factor analyses (MLCFA) were implemented with the *Lavaan* 0.6.6 package (Rosseel, 2012). To compensate for the non-normality of the data, the maximum likelihood estimator (MLR) with the Yuan- Bentler T2* scaled test statistic and robust Huber- White standard errors were applied to recover the parameter estimates for all structural equation models (SEM). The *sirt* package (Robitzsch, 2020) was utilized to implement maximum likelihood (ML) multigroup factor alignment (MLMFA) optimization. Due to the two-stage cluster sampling design, the secondary sampling units (i.e., students nested in schools) were not equiprobably sampled. Thus, specially designed sampling weights were incorporated into the MLCFA and MLMFA analyses to adjust the standard errors (Heeringa et al., 2010). In the current study, TLI and CFI values above 0.95, and SRMR and RMSEA values close to/ below 0.06 (Hu & Bentler, 1999) are considered indicators of meritorious fit of the model-implied covariance matrix to the corresponding data covariance matrix. To establish measurement equivalence, the absolute difference ($|\Delta|$) between the CFI, RMSEA, and SRMR values of the two nested models should not be greater than 0.010, 0.015, and 0.030, respectively (Chen, 2007).

Results

Cross-cultural Comparability of Bullying

Prior to commencing MLCFA to examine the measurement equivalence of bullying across cultures, confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to calibrate the psychometric measure using the average individual-level pooled-within covariance matrix (Fisher & Fontaine, 2011). The CFA model converged normally with the following fit indices' values: $\chi^2_{\text{scaled}}(5) = 8831.252$, $p < 0.001$, $CFI = 0.956$, $TLI = 0.911$, $RMSEA = 0.140$, $SRMR = 0.037$. Generally, the model did not reach optimum levels of model-data fit because of high $RMSEA$ and low TLI values. Subsequently, the modification indices were examined to detect potential sources of misspecification. The largest modification index ($MI = 21647.374$) was considered theoretically plausible because it referred to a correlation between the measurement errors of items 1 and 2. This modification was incorporated in the revised model, which was substantially improved with $\chi^2_{\text{scaled}}(4) = 839.026$, $p < 0.001$, $CFI = 0.996$, $TLI = 0.990$, $RMSEA = 0.048$, $SRMR = 0.010$. The Satorra-Bentler $\Delta\chi^2(1) = 7471$, $p < 0.001$, test indicated a statistically significant improvement in model fit and thus, the revised measurement structure was retained.

The revised model was then reconfigured as a multilevel (two-level) confirmatory factor model (MLCFA). In this way, hypothesis 1 will be tested. It is to be noted that contemporary software provides only the SRMR fit index, which is based on the standardised residual matrices, for both levels separately. Therefore, greater emphasis is placed on the values of this index. The configural model A was exceptionally well-fitting, i.e., $\chi^2_{\text{scaled}}(8) = 102.881$, $p < 0.001$, $CFI = 0.996$, $TLI = 0.991$, $RMSEA = 0.031$, $SRMR_{\text{WITHIN}} = 0.011$, $SRMR_{\text{BETWEEN}} = 0.016$. The information criteria displayed the following values: $AIC = 2051504.706$, and $BIC = 2051698.571$. To examine whether the multilevel (two-level) approach was vindicated, the intraclass correlation coefficient for each item was calculated. All ICCs were above 0.05 and the average ICC (ρ) value was $\rho = 0.062$, which indicates that an MLCFA is fully justified as a means to a cross-cultural investigation of the within- and between-culture equivalence (Stapleton et al., 2016).

In the next model (Model B), the equivalence of the factor loadings (λ_i) was examined across levels. The model with cross-level equality constraints on the factor loadings converged with the following values in goodness-of-fit indices: $\chi^2_{\text{scaled}}(12) = 150.411$, $p < 0.001$,

$CFI= 0.996$, $TLI= 0.994$, $RMSEA= 0.026$, $SRMR_{WITHIN}= 0.011$, $SRMR_{BETWEEN}= 0.036$. The information criteria displayed the following values: $AIC= 2051508.022$, and $BICc= 2051673.166$. As can be seen, model B can be considered invariant because the Δ approximate goodness-of-fit indices (ΔAFI) were within the appropriate limits. Therefore, weak measurement equivalence (also known as metric equivalence) can be assumed to hold. Model B is presented in Figure 1. The within (L1)- and between (L2)-culture factor loadings per item are also provided in Figure 1. Level 2 reliability was equal to $\alpha=0.967$; $\omega_H=0.876$. In the final step of these analyses, we examine whether strong measurement equivalence at the between-culture level holds. This final model (model C) displayed the following goodness-of-fit indices' values: $\chi^2_{scaled}(17)= 104366.720$, $p<0.001$, $CFI= 0.987$, $TLI= 0.985$, $RMSEA= 0.039$, $SRMR_{WITHIN}= 0.011$, $SRMR_{BETWEEN}= 0.113$. The information criteria showed the following values, $AIC= 2055583.561$, and $BICc= 2055712.804$.

Figure 1. *Multilevel (two-level) confirmatory factor analysis with cross-level equality constraints.*

Although model C reached acceptable levels of model-data fit according to the CFI, TLI, and RMSEA indices, the SRMR for the culture level exceeded the 0.06 cut-off. Moreover, the sample adjusted Bayesian ($BICc$) and the Akaike information criteria, that penalise model complexity, indicated that model C was less parsimonious compared to model B. Considering also the fact that the $|\Delta SRMR_{BETWEEN}|$ exceeded by far the cut-off value for meas-

urement equivalence, I reject the hypothesis of strong measurement equivalence and conclude that cross-cultural differences in exposure to bullying are eminent. The ΔAFI s are presented in Table 2 for comparative reasons.

Table 2. (Δ) Approximate Goodness-of-Fit Indices (ΔAFI s) of Measurement Equivalence

Model	<i>CFI</i>	$ \Delta CFI $	<i>RMSEA</i>	$ \Delta RMSEA $	<i>SRMR_{BETWEEN}</i>	$ \Delta SRMR_{BETWEEN} $
Configural Two-Level equivalence (Model A)	0.996		0.031		0.016	
Weak equivalence (Model B)	0.996	0.000	0.026	0.005	0.036	0.020
Strong equivalence (Model C)	0.987	0.009	0.039	0.013	0.113	0.077

Note: $|\Delta SRMR_{WITHIN}|$ can be calculated from the in-text information.

Cross-Cultural Variation in Latent Mean Bullying Scores

In the current section, the results of cross-cultural comparisons of the latent mean scores in bullying across 32 cultures are presented. The findings are taxonomized then according to 8 broad regional clusters to facilitate an interpretation of the position of each cluster. The prior analyses indicated that only the psychological meaning is equivalent across cultures and individuals (weak equivalence). Consequently, comparisons of (latent) mean scores under weak measurement equivalence may be biased. Therefore, *approximate measurement equivalence* via maximum likelihood multigroup factor alignment (MLMFA) optimization (Asparouhov & Muthen, 2014) was implemented to unbiasedly recover latent means for all cultures. In the present study, the MGCFA configural model with one modification (i.e., see above) reached the following fit: $\chi^2_{scaled} (128) = 1752.569, p < 0.001, CFI = 0.991, TLI = 0.977, RMSEA = 0.069, SRMR = 0.015$. To achieve model identification, the *sirt* package in R (R Core Team, 2018) requires the factor mean of one cultural group to be constrained to zero (Robitzsch, 2020). In line with the literature (Asparouhov & Muthen, 2014; Byrne & Van de Vijver, 2017), the group with a factor mean closest to 0.0 can be used as the reference group. Subsequently, to identify the model, South Korea was selected as the reference group because the associated latent mean was near zero ($\alpha = 0.079$).

The results of *approximate equivalence* indicated 0% of non-equivalence in factor loadings and 6.9% of non-equivalence in item intercepts. Finally, the classical goodness-of-fit indices are not available in MLMFA; however, the R^2 is used as an effect size of the extent to which non-equivalence in loading and intercept parameters is attributed to the varying latent factor means and variances (Byrne & Van de Vijver, 2017). R^2 values close to 1.00 indicate a greater degree of equivalence (Asparouhov & Muthen, 2014; Muthen & Asparouhov, 2018). The R^2 effect sizes were $R^2_{\lambda}=.993$ and $R^2_{\nu}=.997$ for the loadings and the intercepts, respectively. Therefore, the recovered factor means based on approximate equivalence can be considered accurate. Schematically, the latent factor means of bullying are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Latent factor means of bullying across countries.

ARE: United Arab Emirates; ARG: Argentina; AUS: Australia; AUT: Austria; BEL: Belgium; BGR: Bulgaria; BRA: Brazil; DNK: Denmark; ESP: Spain; FIN: Finland; FRA: France; GBR: United Kingdom; GRC: Greece; HKG: Hong Kong; HUN: Hungary; IDN: Indonesia; IRL: Ireland, Republic of; ITA: Italy; JPN: Japan; KOR: Korea; MEX: Mexico; NLD: Netherlands; PHL: Philippines; POL: Poland; PRT: Portugal; QCI: China; ROU: Romania; SGP: Singapore; SWE: Sweden; THA: Thailand; TUR: Turkey; USA: United States of America

In short, East Asian countries (Japan, Republic of Korea, China, Hong Kong) were displaying on average among the lowest latent means. On the other hand, Southeastern Asian countries (Philippines, Thailand, Indonesia, Singapore), had on average among the highest latent means. Northern European countries (Finland, France, Denmark, Belgium, Netherlands, Austria, Sweden) had rather low latent mean scores, though slightly higher than those of the East Asian cluster and a lot lower than those of the Southeastern Asian cluster. Eastern European countries (Poland, Hungary, Bulgaria, Romania) had scored higher than Northern European and East Asian countries, though lower than Southeast Asian countries. Portugal and countries that belong to the Mediterranean (Spain, Greece, Italy) and South American (Brazil, Argentina, Mexico) regions were also manifesting on average higher latent means; that is, their scores were comparatively higher than those of the East Asian and Northern European clusters. Anglo-Saxon countries (USA, United Kingdom, Ireland, Australia) were mainly among the higher scoring. Despite this, their scores were lower than those of the Southeast Asian cluster and higher than those of the North European and East Asian clusters. The United Arab Emirates and Turkey, representing the Middle East region, displayed rather high latent factor mean scores. The latent factor means according to the regional clusters are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Latent factor means according to the regional clusters

To compare the latent factor means across the four *cultural* clusters (i.e., honour-based, Confucian-based, and Eastern European collectivism; individualism), descriptive sta-

tistics were computed based on the latent factor means. The classification of the national cultures was based on Hofstede et al. (2010), House et al. (2004), and Uskul et al. (2010, 2013). On average, the Confucian-based collectivist cluster's score was the lowest ($M=0.312$). Rather higher was the score of the honour-based collectivist cluster ($M=0.559$). Even higher was the score of the Eastern European collectivist cluster ($M=0.746$). Surprisingly, individualistic countries scored approximately the same as the Confucian-based collectivist cluster ($M=0.485$).

Discussion and conclusion

To sum up, the first part of this study concerned the extent to which bullying can be considered comparable between cultures. This first preliminary step is of great importance because we cannot be assured that the psychological meaning has not undergone a shift during the transition to the between-culture level of analysis. Although our analyses' results support the between-culture equivalence of the psychological meaning of bullying, cross-cultural differences were found because strong measurement equivalence was not supported (see Table 2). Thus, hypothesis 1, which concerns the measurement equivalence of bullying across cultures, was partially confirmed, whereas hypothesis 2, which pertained to the existence of cross-cultural differences, was confirmed. This level of 'weak' equivalence, though, is sufficient enough to permit intracultural comparisons and cross-cultural comparisons of regressive effects and correlations (Vieluf et al., 2013). The existence of cross-cultural variation in bullying indicates that other factors beyond the latent variable (Kline, 2016) determine students' bullying victimization in each country (see model C). Even though this bias is troubling for cross-cultural comparisons of scores (Van de Vijver & Leung, 2011), it offers also the opportunity to search and identify possible eco-cultural variables that account for the unexplained cultural variation (Poortinga et al., 2002). Therefore, in the present study, the cultural value of individualism (vs. collectivism) was considered as a possible variable that differentiates students' exposure to bullying.

Moreover, in the second part of the present study, a more nuanced and highly advanced structural equation modelling technique was applied, namely the alignment optimization method (Asparouhov & Muthen, 2014). This method allowed me to unbiasedly estimate the latent factor means of bullying for all the cultural groups herein, despite the absence of strong measurement equivalence. By opting for this approach, I was able to understand better

and with more precision the cross-cultural differences based on the latent variable itself, instead of comparing observed composite scores saturated with measurement error. The cluster aggregates, as presented in Figure 3, indicated that the lowest latent factor mean scores were observed in East Asian countries, where the cultural value of collectivism is prevalent. Even though Southeast Asian countries are also characterized by an in-group orientation (see Hofstede et al., 2010), these countries' students were the most exposed to bullying. This may suggest that other country-level factors (e.g., economic inequality; affluence and prosperity levels- for a similar discussion see Pörhölä et al., 2016) beyond the cultural value of individualism (vs. collectivism) determine these countries' scores on this bullying scale. Honour-based collectivist nations, such as Greece, Spain, Italy, Mexico, Turkey, Brazil, Portugal, United Arab Emirates, and Argentina, were characterized by rather higher latent mean scores compared to the Confucian-based collectivist nations (e.g., Japan, China, Korea, Hong Kong). Eastern European countries generally score more on the collectivist pole; however, they are neither honour-bound nor Confucian-based (Vieluf et al., 2013). The scores of Eastern European collectivist countries were also quite high. Thus, hypothesis 3 was rejected. Although highly individualistic countries, such as the United States of America (USA), the United Kingdom (UK), Ireland, Australia, Austria, and Denmark, had mainly among the highest latent mean scores, the average score of the individualistic cultural cluster was *higher* than the Confucian-based collectivist cluster but *lower* than that of the other two types of collectivist clusters. Thus, hypothesis 4 was rejected.

At this point, it should be mentioned that these findings seem to corroborate with those of Migliaccio and Raskauskas (2015) concerning the differences between highly individualistic and collectivist countries. However, as was underscored in the present study, the research question should be framed within a more culture-specific context by recognising the existence of cultural sub-clusters even within the broad cultural group of collectivist nations. Contrary, though, to the results of Smith and Robinson (2019), I found that the inverse link between individualism and bullying is differentiated based on the subtype of collectivism. Specifically, highly individualistic nations score lower than the honour-based and East European collectivist clusters; however, the scores of the countries belonging to the individualistic cluster are higher than those of the Confucian-based collectivist cluster. Thus, it is recommended that researchers should avoid overgeneralizations to all collectivist nations.

Conclusion

To conclude, the present study had two main goals. The first goal was to examine the extent to which bullying was comparable across different cultures, whereas the second objective was to identify whether culture differentiates students' bullying scores. In short, it was found that school bullying is similarly construed by students across cultures, despite that, cross-cultural differences in bullying are apparent. It was further shown that these differences can be attributed in part to the cultural value of individualism (Hofstede et al., 2010; House et al., 2004) since the countries' classification as individualistic vs collectivist distinguishes the scores on the bullying scale. One implication of these findings is that educational system-wide interventions aimed to reduce school bullying should also consider the specific cultural context. Additionally, it is underscored that cross-cultural comparisons in absence of strong measurement equivalence should be interpreted with caution since participants in different national groups may not have the same latent trait level and, thus, score differently on bullying. Therefore, it is important to consider the degree of bias while formulating educational policy to ameliorate the school bullying problem. Regarding the implications for future research, the following may be applicable.

It is generally very difficult to understand how the cultural value of individualism (vs. collectivism) may influence students' experiences of bullying. However, the results herein indicated heterogeneity among three different subtypes of collectivist cultural clusters. Specifically, it is underscored that future research should delve deeper into the cross-cultural differences in bullying, and how these discrepancies may be better understood by considering the different types of collectivism. This stems from the fact that Confucian-based collectivist countries (i.e., East Asian countries) have lower rates of bullying than Southeast Asian countries, which are also described by high collectivism. Lastly, future research may focus on "unpackaging" the effects of culture (Bond & Van de Vijver, 2011) on bullying by also considering socio-economic country-level variables.

Limitations

It should always be kept in mind that in the present study, a comparatively large sample from many nations with varying cultural orientations was selected from the overall database. That does not mean, though, that other countries in the same cultural clusters, which were not considered herein, display the same pattern of latent factor mean differences. Addi-

tionally, we cannot be assured that the cultural value of individualism (vs. collectivism) is causally responsible for the cross-cultural differences that were observed. In other words, the present study was quite limited in scope because only a specific cultural orientation was considered. From a technical perspective, the following limitations should be mentioned. Even though a random coefficient two-level confirmatory factor model could have been applied to identify which items function differentially (DIF) between cultures, regrettably that method is currently unavailable in the *Lavaan* 0.6.6 software (Rosseel, 2012). Moreover, the discrepancies among Confucian-based, honour-based, and East European collectivist clusters were based on descriptive statistics, which means that far more powerful modelling techniques could have been utilised to delve deeper into what drives these cross-cultural differences. Furthermore, I note that a comparative multilevel analysis of the predictors of bullying could shed more light on the cultural differences between the different cultural and geographical clusters.

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